

**OPEN
KNOWLEDGE
MAPS**

EOSC
secretariat.eu

Setup and management of the EOSC Secretariat
supporting the EOSC Governance

CoVis: a curated, collaborative & visual knowledge base for COVID-19 research

Authors:	Peter Kraker (Open Knowledge Maps), Girija Goyal (ReFigure), Maxi Schramm (Open Knowledge Maps), James Akin (ReFigure), Christopher Kittel (Open Knowledge Maps)
Version:	1.0

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Open Knowledge Maps and ReFigure is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

This project is financially supported by EOSCsecretariat.eu. EOSCsecretariat.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019, grant agreement number 831644.

Abstract

For the development of therapeutics and vaccines for COVID-19, scientists depend on valid knowledge on the coronavirus biology, clinical responses and epidemiology. But finding reliable research results is often difficult: with over 200,000 papers published on the topic, scientists spend a lot of valuable time reviewing the literature.

CoVis is addressing this challenge: the tool provides a curated knowledge map of seminal works on COVID-19. CoVis provides a quick overview of seminal research outputs from key areas of biomedical research. When pertinent issues are not answered by a single research source, such as whether a drug is effective, data and images from multiple sources are compiled into a visual dashboard called a ReFigure. The collection is not meant to be exhaustive, but to offer a single reference point for definitive research in key areas of biomedical research.

CoVis makes it easier to get started on coronavirus research - but also helps you to stay up-to-date. In order to do justice to the rapid development of COVID-19 research, the database is extended regularly by a dedicated team of curators. Subject-matter experts from around the world are invited to contribute to CoVis in a number of ways. They can provide feedback and propose research resources for inclusion in the map using a short form. They can join the curation or create their own ReFigures and interpretations of research findings for inclusion in the knowledge map.

Developed in collaboration between Open Knowledge Maps and ReFigure, CoVis establishes a meaningful link between the two infrastructures, combining powerful visual overview and knowledge synthesis components and offering them to stakeholders of COVID-19 research as an open infrastructure.

1 Introduction and motivation

In the current pandemic, researchers seek valid scientific data and findings on Covid-19 [R1]. In the first few weeks of the crisis alone, hundreds of articles, preprints and datasets were published and this number has expanded manifold. By now, there are more than 200,000 publications on the topic alone, complemented by tens of thousands of other research outputs [R2]. Given the fast pace of research and the limited historical data on COVID-19, many findings are under debate and only understandable after reading several reports from different sources.

Many laboratories have pivoted to Covid-19 research without prior experience of coronavirus biology or adequate preparation. They were immediately confronted with two discovery challenges: (1) having to identify relevant knowledge from unfamiliar (sub-)disciplines with their own terminology and publication culture, and (2) having to keep up with the rapid growth of data and publications and being able to filter out relevant findings [R3]. Both challenges pose significant problems for researchers, leading to delays, unnecessarily duplicated work, and findings that are based on questionable prior results [R4].

Thus, researchers need a reliable, curated starting point for discovery. Current list-based search methods are tedious, time consuming and do not allow the researcher to focus on an area of interest [R5]. Further, the findings may only be understood by reading several articles on multiple different websites. This is where CoVis, the knowledge map of COVID-19 research, comes in: it provides researchers with access and links to the key scientific data and findings, curated by experts. The visual interface allows the user to explore a large number of resources with ease on a single page and all the publications are linked; those that are open access can be downloaded directly from the interface.

2 Concept and design

CoVis is a curated, collaborative & visual knowledge base for Covid-19 research. It can be accessed via <https://openknowledgemaps.org/covis>. Its main interface is a knowledge map (Fig. 1). Knowledge maps provide an instant overview of a topic by showing the main areas at a glance, and resources related to each area annotated with keywords, comments and tags. This makes it possible to easily identify useful, pertinent information.

Disciplines are displayed as bubbles. By clicking on one of the bubbles, users can inspect the resources assigned to it. The size of the bubbles is relative to the number of resources assigned to it. Closeness of bubbles implies subject similarity. The closer two bubbles, the closer they are subject-wise. Centrality of bubbles implies subject similarity with the rest of the map, not importance. The closer a bubble is to the center, the closer it is subject-wise to all the other bubbles in the map.

Currently, the knowledge map is divided into seven key areas of biomedical research (“Diagnostics”, “Epidemiology”, “Host biology and clinical findings”, “Immunity”, “Therapeutics”, “Vaccines”, “Viral Biology”). After careful review and discussion with our users, we added two additional areas, which include foundational papers in coronavirus research to those who have no prior background (“Introduction to coronavirus research” and “Introduction to SARS-COV2 research”).

Fig. 1 - The main interface of CoVis: the COVID-19 knowledge map

Each area has a selection of seminal outputs attached to it (Fig. 2). Outputs have relevant metadata attached to them and they are further contextualised with keywords, comments, and tags provided by the curation team. Output types include datasets, journal articles, preprints, reviews and ReFigures. A ReFigure (Fig 3) is a user-generated collection of figures from different scientific publications. They may be created to address a specific hypothesis, or might be a collection of results that are tied together by a single element (e.g. SARS-CoV-2 pre-clinical models, or validated anti-spike protein antibody clones). ReFigure is open source and free to use and ReFigures can be created by anyone.

The research outputs in CoVis are curated by an editorial team of biomedical experts. The editorial team uses a collaborative spreadsheet as a knowledge base. As soon as outputs are marked for inclusion in the map, they are automatically added to the knowledge map. Users that are viewing the knowledge map are alerted of new content via a notification, similar to those that appear on news websites when a novel piece is published. Users can then choose to reload the page or dismiss the notification and do it later.

Apart from the knowledge map, CoVis provides a landing page with basic information on the project before accessing the knowledge map. CoVis also provides pages with more information on the data source, the team and an FAQ page. It also provides detailed information on how to contact the curation team and the project team, and provides a dedicated form for suggesting new resources or providing feedback.

Area: Therapeutics
[Back to overview](#)

Hide list (15 items)

Search within map... show: Any sort by: Date

Open access

An ultra-high affinity synthetic nanobody blocks SARS-CoV-2 infection by locking Spike into an inactive conformation
 Michael Schörf Bryan Faust, Reuben A Saunders, Smriti Sangwan, Veronica Rezel, Nick Boone Hoppe, Christian Bache Billesbelle, Marcell Zimanyi, Ishan Deshpande, Jiahao Liang, Aditya A Anand, Hiv Dobzinski, Beth Shoshana Zha, Benjamin Barzi-Rhyne, Vladizir Belty, Andrew W Barrie-Hill, Sayan Gupta, Camille R Smonneau, Kristoffer Leon, Kris M White, Silke Block, Yawei Liu, Hevan J Kroger, Corie Y Baltzer, Daniel L Sweeney, Adolfo Garcia-Sastre, Melanie Ott, Marco Vignuzzi, Walter QCRG Structural Biology Consortium, Aashish Manglik in *Biorxiv* (2020-08-08)
<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.08.08.238469v1>
 Document type: Preprint
 Without an effective prophylactic solution, infections from SARS-CoV-2 continue to rise worldwide with devastating health and economic costs. SARS-CoV-2 gains entry into host cells via an interaction between its Spike protein and the host cell receptor...
 "This pre-print describes synthetic nanobodies that could be converted into a dry powder and aerosolized, potentially making the therapeutic self-administered and usable prophylactically. However, follow-up studies in animals and humans are needed." by Megan Sperry, PhD
 Keywords: spike protein; therapeutic; single-domain antibodies; nanobodies; ACE2
 Area: Therapeutics

Open access

Inhibition of PI3Kγ kinase prevents infection by Zaire ebolavirus and SARS-CoV-2
 Yuan-Lin Kang, Yi-Ying Chou, Paul W Rothlauf, Zhuoming Liu, Timothy R Soh, David Cureton, James Brett Case, Rita F Chen, Michael S Diamond, Sean P J Whelan, Tom Kirchhausen in *National Academy of Sciences* (2020-08-06)
<https://www.pnas.org/content/117/34/20803>
 Document type: Journal Article
 Virus entry is a multistep process. It initiates when the virus attaches to the host cell and ends when the viral contents reach the cytosol. Genetically unrelated viruses can subvert analogous subcellular mechanisms and use similar trafficking pathways...
 "Based on this work, AI Therapeutics announced a new randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study with apilimod." by Megan Sperry, PhD
 Keywords: n/a
 Area: Therapeutics

Open access

Retrospective Multicenter Cohort Study Shows Early Interferon Therapy Is Associated with Favorable Clinical Outcomes in COVID-19 Patients

Fig. 2 - The contents of the area "Therapeutics" in the COVID-19 knowledge map

REfigure "Five trials evaluating hydroxychloroquine in COVID-19 patients"

Search

Caption: Figure 1. Percentage of patients with PCR-positive nasopharyngeal swabs over time for Control (black line) and Hydroxychloroquine (red line) groups. The Hydroxychloroquine group shows a significant decrease in PCR positivity compared to the Control group.

Notes: Reduced number of patients positive by qPCR for virus in H...

Authors: PhilippeGautretab\$Jean-ChristopheLagierac\$PhilippePar...

Article DOI: 10.1016/j.jantimicag.2020.105949

Article URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950423020301501>

Legend:

Caption: image0012.png

Notes: This report shows little difference between the control arm ...

Authors: CHEN Jun, LIU Danping, LIU Li, LIU Ping, XU Qingnian, XIA ...

Article DOI: <http://subject.med.wanfangdata.com.cn/Upload/Files...>

Article URL: https://figshare.com/articles/image0012_png/120417...

Legend: Abstract from a trial reporting HCQ use in COVID-19 patient...

Five trials evaluating hydroxychloroquine in COVID-19 patients

Creator [Joe Akin](#)

Created at 3/27/2020

Last visit 2/17/2021

Total 5 images

This ReFigure shows the results of five trials (in chronological order) with hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) in COVID-19 patients.

1. Single arm study in France, n = 26 patients
2. Randomized control trial (RCT) in Shanghai, n = 30 patients
3. RCT in China (viral clearance outcome), n = 62
4. RCT in China (viral clearance outcome), n = 150
5. Real world evidence study in France, n = 173

The first two studies looked at similar time points for clearance of virus. While the first study suggested a dramatic reduction of virus after drug treatment, the second study did not confirm this. The third study supported HCQ use to speed recovery by clinical outcomes. The fourth study found no difference in viral clearance with HCQ use over standard of care. The fifth study asked from observational data whether COVID-19 patients who are treated with HCQ within 48 hours of being admitted have a lower rate of transfer to the intensive care unit (ICU), or

Fig. 3 - Refigure "Five trials evaluating hydroxychloroquine in COVID-19 patients"

In the next two sections of this report, we will provide further information on the underlying technologies as well as community and content management.

This project is financially supported by EOSCsecretariat.eu. EOSCsecretariat.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019, grant agreement number 831644.

3 Technology

The knowledge map is based on the award-winning open-source software Head Start [R6] developed by Open Knowledge Maps. Head Start is capable of creating knowledge maps from a variety of data, including text, metadata and references. The analytics core written in R clusters documents according to their subject similarity, calculates the two-dimensional positioning of documents, and generates a content summary for each cluster. This map representation is then stored in a PostgreSQL database, where it can be versioned.

The visual interface allows the user to explore a large number of resources with ease on a single page; those that are open access can be downloaded directly from the interface. The client component is delivered as a JavaScript package written in React, which is built with NPM and packaged with webpack.

In CoVis, we extended Head Start with a connector to Google Sheets, where metadata, annotations and comments are collected. In particular, we connect to the Sheets via a Python-API which retrieves metadata from the associated data source, performs basic data cleaning, validation and metadata enrichment before handing it over to the analytics core. The connector frequently checks the Google Drive API for updates of the spreadsheet. Once an update has been detected, the knowledge map is recalculated and a new revision is written to the database. In the future, we want to implement a more open, integrated editing component, but for now, this provides us with a quick and reasonable intermediate solution for an otherwise complex and difficult to implement feature.

On the frontend, we extended the knowledge map interface to be able to display curation comments and tags. We also added the ability to detect server updates and trigger an update notification, which is achieved by periodically polling a specified endpoint on the server using an AJAX call. Furthermore, validation errors from the data connector can now be displayed under the knowledge map for the benefit of the curation team. This functionality is enabled by adding validation information to the map metadata and throwing a dedicated event once the data is loaded, which can be picked up by the page that embeds the knowledge map.

The developed system has proven to be very stable despite frequent activity by the curation team and high interest by users. In total, 831 revisions have been created after updates to the CoVis database. Since the first release of the CoVis platform in June 2020, we recorded more than 13,000 page views on CoVis.

4 Community and content management

The articles, datasets and ReFigures in CoVis are curated by an editorial team of biomedical experts (Fig. 3). In order to do justice to the rapid development of COVID-19 research, the database is extended regularly in curation meetings. Resources are nominated based on the interest of the individual contributor and posed for inclusion along with the rationale for inclusion. The nominated resources are discussed as to their exhibited impact, or potential impact for moving the field forward. When the editorial team reaches a consensus, the resource is included in the knowledge map.

The editorial team is led by immunologists and ReFigure founders Dr. Girija Goyal and Dr. James Akin, who also formed the starting database curation team. Subject-matter experts from around the world are invited to contribute to CoVis in a number of ways. They can provide feedback and propose research resources for

inclusion in the map using a short form, and join the curation team. Another avenue for collaboration is to create an own ReFigures and interpretations of research findings for inclusion in the knowledge map.

Since the start, four more members have joined the curation team, and further experts from institutions such as the Wyss Institute Coronavirus Therapeutics team and the Indiana School of Medicine have provided input. Together with resources from other resources such as academic social media, search engines and news items, the curation team has reviewed hundreds of relevant outputs in finding seminal outputs. Close to 200 have been entered for discussion in the knowledge base, of which 108 have been selected for inclusion in the knowledge map (67 journal articles, 24 preprints, 9 reviews, and 7 datasets). For seven key issues, such as the prevalence of antibodies in symptomatic and asymptomatic groups, the curation team has created ReFigures, which provide a synthesis of another set of findings (32 in total).

The collection is not meant to be exhaustive, but to offer a single reference point for definitive research in key areas of biomedical research. As such, it is now being used as a training resource in biomedical laboratories for researchers and students who are new to the topic.

Fig. 4 - The CoVis curation team

5 Openness

CoVis is an open infrastructure following the principles of open science and can therefore be fully reused. Unless otherwise noted, all content on CoVis is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The CoVis database is made available under CC0 (Public Domain Dedication). The software to CoVis is open source under an MIT license and hosted on Github (see <https://github.com/OpenKnowledgeMaps/covis>).

6 Outlook and further exploitation of results

CoVis is an ongoing effort that continues beyond the runtime of the EOSC Secretariat project. The curation team has regular meetings and provides frequent updates to the knowledge base. CoVis is Open Knowledge Maps' first foray into collaboratively edited knowledge maps. The project allowed us to pilot reader curated knowledge maps and a major result of this effort has been the interest from public agencies and research groups in curating and sharing knowledge maps. In the future, we want to implement a more open, integrated editing component within our knowledge maps. For now, we have generalized the CoVis approach in a prototype for creating knowledge maps based on arbitrary Google Sheets. Given further funding, this opens up the possibility of creating CoVis-type platforms for arbitrary topics in the future.

Together with the now-established link between Open Knowledge Maps and ReFigure, this would bring a standardized way of providing powerful visual overview and synthesis that can be quickly deployed in case of situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the future, further knowledge maps on COVID are also planned. Initial ideas include branching out the host biology and clinical findings area, which already includes a significant number of resources, into its own map. In addition, several institutions and projects have expressed interest in curating their own knowledge map on COVID-19 related topics. These include knowledge maps on specialized areas such as animal models, or for different audiences such as laypersons. To accommodate these future extensions, we have already developed a version of the website that can handle multiple knowledge maps.

We have also planned to integrate and interlink our effort with further COVID-19 platforms such as the COVID-19 Data Portal [R7], the Trusted World of Corona (TWOC), or the OpenAIRE COVID-19 Open Research Gateway [R2].

A broad impact of this effort has been the learning on human curation of scientific data. We identified paradigms and unmet needs in curating a corpus of meaningful information on any topic. For instance, how to include and disseminate preprints or the level of reproducibility and/or supporting information that is necessary to consider a finding actionable. This has led to new connections with other groups on potential collaborations on scientific curation. Further, the curation team is now debating if and how to present emerging or novel insights which may not be considered seminal but may be critical to understand the topic.

7 References

No	Description/Link
R1	Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2020, March 17). A fiasco in the making? As the coronavirus pandemic takes hold, we are making decisions without reliable data. STAT. https://www.statnews.com/2020/03/17/a-fiasco-in-the-making-as-the-coronavirus-pandemic-takes-hold-we-are-making-decisions-without-reliable-data/
R2	See https://covid-19.openaire.eu/ [05.03.2021]
R3	Johnson, C. Y. (2020). Inside a lab where scientists are working urgently to fight the coronavirus outbreak. Washington Post. Retrieved October 12, 2020, from https://www.washingtonpost.com/science/2020/02/14/inside-lab-where-scientists-are-working-urgently-fight-coronavirus-outbreak/
R4	OECD. (2020). Why open science is critical to combatting COVID-19. OECD Policy Responses to Coronavirus (COVID-19). http://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/why-open-science-is-critical-to-combatting-covid-19-cd6ab2f9/
R5	Kraker, P., Schramm, M., & Kittel, C. (2021). Discoverability in (a) Crisis. ABI Technik, 41(1), 3–12. https://doi.org/10.1515/abitech-2021-0003
R6	Peter Kraker, Christopher Kittel, Maxi Schramm, Thomas Arrow, Scott Chamberlain, Rainer Bachleitner, Asura Enkhbayar, Yael Stein, Philipp Weissensteiner & Open Knowledge Maps team and contributors. (2020, February 5). OpenKnowledgeMaps/Headstart: Headstart 6 (Version v6). Zenodo. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3641795
R7	https://www.covid19dataportal.org/

